

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D5.7 Data Management Plan v1.0

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			Updated information on data collected per WP per partner are also included.	
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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
AAM	Accepted Author Manuscript
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
CC	Creative Commons
CERN	The European Organization for Nuclear Research (Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire)
CSL	Citation Style Language
DIT	Data Information Tables
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPIA	Data Privacy Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Directive
IP	Intellectual Property
ISAN	International Standard Audio-Visual Number
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
ISRC	International Standard Recording Code
ISSN	International Standard Serial Number
ISTC	International Standard Text Code
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SWORD	Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the first version of the 5G-ROUTES Data Management Plan (DMP) and responds to Task T5.3 – Innovation, data management and IPR activities (WP5). This document includes information covering all the areas below:

- The guiding principles for data management in the project
- The legal framework constituted by the General Data Protection Directive (GDPR)
- Data Summary: Overview of what data will be gathered and processed in the project (including, where applicable, personal data)
- How data will be stored and processed according to the H2020 Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) Data Management principles, making data: findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.
- Resource allocation: The costs of making data FAIR in this project.
- Data Security: How we intend to keep the data secure and how that can be shared with the public.
- Appointment of Data Protection Officer (DPO) per partner

These procedures have formalized and applied the *FAIR* data management framework, as per the EC guidelines, with the goal of making data openly accessible and interoperable and addressing data re-use considerations. According to the EU Guidelines for Data Management Plans (DMPs), the DMP governs all data generated and collected during the project, the standards to be used, how research data will be preserved and what parts of the datasets will be shared for verification or re-use. The 5G-ROUTE DMP sets out the grounds for identifying, curing, publishing, and sharing reusable data assets for research.

The DMP provides the obligation to protect individuals' personal data originating from data collection and /or analysis of project's key parameters, in compliance with applicable privacy and data protection laws and regulations. This is done by framing mechanisms in collaboration with participating partners and ensuring that security measures and policies are in place to safeguard the programme from personal data risks of breach.

In addition, 5G-ROUTES takes an active role on the Open Research Data Pilot (ORD Pilot) [1], a H2020 EU Pilot Program aimed at enhancing access and reuse of research data produced by Horizon 2020 projects, developing research methodologies to ensure that the types of data created or collected by the project are suitable for open access after project closure. 5G-ROUTES will use the open research data repository Zenodo and Open Research Europe to comply with the Horizon 2020 Open Access Mandate. This mandate applies to the underlying research data of publications, but beneficiaries can also voluntarily make other datasets open. In 5G-ROUTES, all deliverables, publications, and the anonymous parts of the underlying datasets will be uploaded to the European Commission Funded Research (OpenAIRE) Community in Zenodo and Open Research Europe. Uploads will be done upon approval of the deliverables by the European Commission, upon publication or acceptance of scientific publications, or, for underlying datasets, at the end of the project at the latest.

The DMP is a living document and will be updated at the end of the project to reflect the actual research data generated during the project and include updated instructions for how to access open data. Day-to-day data management and monitoring will be done using an excel file in Teamwork (project's file repository) that will be continuously updated to reflect actual data generation.

2 Introduction

2.1 Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs

The purpose of this chapter is to map 5G-ROUTES' Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to 5G-ROUTES's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	5G-ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
<i>D5.7: Data Management Plan v1.0</i>	<i>Initial plan for data management</i>	<i>Chapters 3-5 Annexes 1-3</i>	<i>As below</i>
TASKS			
<i>Task T5.3 – Innovation, data management and IPR activities</i>	<i>Data Management Plan (DMP) [TTU]: Development of the DMP, which will contain information related to the types of data the project will generate and collect, the standards that will be used to represent the data during the project and how partners might exploit the data resulting from the project. The DMP will set robust management procedures that will protect personal data collected as a result of project activities, as well as client owned data, from unauthorised use or sharing, also supporting GDPR compliance. In addition, the DMP will include a data protection impact assessment of 5G-ROUTES's requirements and field trials that will be used to ensure the project takes a data protection-by-design approach. The DMP will be produced at M06 and finalised in M33. The project's Data Protection Officer (DPO) will be available to assist - if needed - in decision-making as 5GROUTES is developed to identify potential risks,</i>	<i>Chapters 3-5 Annexes 1-3</i>	<i>Chapter 2: Introduction of the deliverable and mapping with project outputs Chapter 3: Data Management Overview including Ethics and GDPR Compliance, procedures, open access and handling of personal data approach, FAIR Data Management compliance. Chapter 4: Data Lifecycle and Related Procedures. Initial DMP overview on collected data per WP/partner Chapter 7: Conclusions</i>

	<i>mitigation solutions and support compliance. All partners have appointed their own internal DPO who will closely collaborate with the project's DPO.</i>		
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2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

In this chapter a description of the Deliverable's Structure is provided, outlining the respective Chapters and their content. A summary of the report structure and chapters of this report is presented below:

- Chapter 1: Executive summary.
- Chapter 2: Introduction of the deliverable and mapping with other project outputs (i.e. deliverables).
- Chapter 3: Data management approach following in the project, including Ethics and GDPR Compliance, procedures, open access, handling of personal data and comply with FAIR Data Management.
- Chapter 4: Data Lifecycle and related procedures. Also includes roles and responsibilities and an initial DMP overview on data collected per WP/partner.
- Chapter 5: Conclusions.

The report also includes annexes such as:

- Annex 1: Template used for appointment of DPO per partner
- Annex 2: List with DPO per partner
- Annex 3: Data Protection Policy

2.3 Linkage to other project outputs

In this section the interdependencies with other project activities are specified, like the deliverables from which this report utilized inputs and the deliverables to which this report provides its outputs.

Important: *In case this report is a PUBLIC deliverable you should make sure that no confidential information from contributing/benefitting deliverables is described below.*

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	Deliverable Chapter(s)	Contribution and Value of linkage
INPUTS from other deliverables utilised in this report		
D7.7 Legal Framework-Ethics-Gender-Balance v1.0	Annexes V, VI, VII, VIII and IX	The following are the templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets obligatory to be used when conducting trials involving participants from outside the consortium: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informed consent form example template • Anonymous Informed Consent Template • Non-Anonymous Informed Consent Template
D8.1 H – Requirement No.1	Section 5: Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets	

		<p>The templates were initially established and included in 5G-ROUTES D7.7¹ and are part of the Ethics Protocol. In addition to the above templates, the following template is an additional template exists in D8.1 H – Requirement No.1 (Dissemination Level: CO):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-Disclosure Agreement for External Advisory Board Members <p>Those templates are also referred in this document, in Section 3.2, to have a synchronization between the Data Management Plan and Ethics and make sure that data collection is based on ethics requirements.</p>
OUTPUTS from this report utilised by other deliverables		
D8.2 POPD - Requirement No. 2	<p>Section 3: Data Management Overview</p> <p>Section 5.1: Roles and Responsibilities Regarding the Data Management Plan</p> <p>Annex 1: DPO Appointment Template</p> <p>Section 6: 5G-ROUTES Data Overview per WP</p>	<p>D8.2 (Dissemination Level: CO) has the below listed references to D5.7:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appointment of Data Protection Officers (DPOs) • Data management approach • Data Information Table for collecting information from partners <p>The expected benefit of utilizing the above information into the D8.2 is to connect the Data Management Plan during the set out of the 'ethics requirements' that the project must comply with.</p>

¹ 5G-ROUTES D7.7: https://www.5g-routes.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/5G-ROUTES-D-7.7-LEGAL-FRAMEWORK-ETHICS-GENDER-BALANCE_2020-11-30_v1.0.pdf

3 Data Management Approach

3.1 Overview

This chapter provides an overview of the guiding principles which will be used to manage research data during and beyond the 5G-ROUTES project's lifetime. It also defines the data collection concepts and data purposes and provides a detailed description of the procedures for data collection, protection, and publication, which will be implemented to successfully carry out this project task.

As the project this overview will be revisited and updated (if needed) in subsequent iterations of the DMP. The topic of data management is an important theme of the agenda of the monthly project meetings and will continue to be in the future. This is to ensure that EBOS (with the support of ILS) is kept up to date of any changes to the partners' plans regarding their use of data and this document can be updated whenever necessary.

Figure 1: 5G-ROUTES Data Management Plan

Figure 1 shows the data management approach followed in the 5G-ROUTES project. Data that will be collected, created, and distributed within each of the 5G-ROUTES WPs are defined and grouped by research, tests, documentation, reporting and management files. Data types may include trials raw data (datasets), narrative texts, numbers, images, audio files, video files, internal/external reports, KPIs, statistics, figures, questionnaires, check lists, user input/feedback, etc. Such data, in an aggregated format, will be stored in a designated and secured data storage; to be further used as input to project work and provide basis for the analysis in deliverables, scientific publications and the exploitation activities ([Section 3.4](#)).

Data collected throughout the project will continuously be assessed for:

1. Compliance with Ethics and GDPR as described in D7.7 Legal Framework-Ethics-Gender-Balance v1.0.
2. Eligibility for dissemination and publication.
3. Suitability for IP protection and exploitation.

3.2 Ethics and GDPR compliance

The 5G-ROUTES project will touch on privacy and data protection issues by collecting data from project participants from EU countries. The following are the templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets obligatory to be used when conducting trials involving participants from outside the consortium:

- Informed consent form example template
- Anonymous Informed Consent Template
- Non-Anonymous Informed Consent Template

The above-mentioned templates were initially established and included in D7.7 and are part of the Ethics Protocol. In addition to the above templates, the following template exists in D8.1 H – Requirement No.1:

- Non-Disclosure Agreement for External Advisory Board Members

Chapter 6 - 5G-ROUTES Data Management Overview per WP, provides a list of all data/datasets currently expected to be generated in the 5G-ROUTES project and their planned accessibility. This list will be developed as the project progresses.

The Global Data Protection Policy (the “Policy”) is drafted by EBOS regarding the Project 5G-ROUTES Contract Number 951867 (the “Project”) executed by the list of partners included therein (the “Project Partners”) to comply with:

- The policy and legal requirements of the EU General Data Protection Regulation: EU 2016/679 (the “GDPR”), as in effect since 25 May 2018.
- All other applicable national and EU regulations and guidelines on personal data processing.
- Applicable regulations and best practices with regards to research projects within the EU H2020 Research Programme.

The following chapters describe the related procedures applied in the 5G-ROUTES project. Moreover, GDPR applies to all personal data collected during the implementation of project activities. Detailed information about the policy can be found in [Annex 3](#).

5G-ROUTES comply with the GDPR needs for creating several process related policies so that there is an overall agreement of the data used, stored, etc. during the daily project activities. For that reason, the following Table includes such an information and processes for the Consortium (as those have been agreed between the partners) to be followed.

Table 2: Daily Data Usage and Processes

Process	Description
Contacts information	The 5G-ROUTES list of contacts is a single .XLS file which includes the following information about all the consortium partners: Name, Surname, Email address, Role in the Project, and the emailing lists that belongs to. This file is stored in the cloud file repository of the Project (Teamwork) with restricted access only to consortium partners (via login). The purpose of this list is to keep organised all consortium contacts into a single location. The data of this list will be used mostly for communication purposes and will be kept for 5 years duration.
Meeting's material	This is related to any document created and used for the purposes of project meetings like agendas, presentations, minutes, signature lists. All these documents will be stored in the cloud file repository of the Project (Teamwork - under the meetings section) with restricted access only to consortium partners (via login). Those documents will be kept for 5 years duration.
Workshops and training material	These data relate to the organisation of workshops like agendas, participants' lists, etc. and training material (i.e. presentations, video recordings, photos, etc.) related to the Project. In case there is a need to external publish this material, this should be fully anonymized so that it excludes any personal information. All these documents will be stored in the cloud file repository of the Project (Teamwork - under the workshops section) with restricted access only to consortium partners (via login). This material will be kept for 5 years duration.

Process	Description
Dissemination material	Unless otherwise expressly specified in Project contract, Project Coordinator shall be responsible for the personal data processing carried out for Project dissemination purposes (newsletters, social media, and other dissemination) to (1) Collect and keep all relevant personal data; (2) Monitor relevant communications; (3) Address to partners instructions and guidelines on Project dissemination activities; (4) Inform partners of any policy or legal requirements reviews and changes.
Reporting material	This is related to documents prepared for internal and external (to the EC) Project progress activities, technical overviews etc. Related documents with financial information sometimes including personal data. The purpose of these data is for partners to claim budget requests for their related effort in the Project and will be maintained by the Project Coordinator and stored in the cloud file repository of the Project (Teamwork). This material will be kept for 5 years duration.
Deliverables, internal documents, and other reports	During the 5G-ROUTES project lifetime, all documentation and reporting related to the project (i.e. deliverables, internal documents, etc.) will be used for the project contractual obligations and shared to: Consortium partners, EC, or publicly, depending on their deliverable type. All these documents will be stored in the cloud file repository of the Project (Teamwork - under the Deliverable/docs section) with restricted access only to consortium partners (via login). Public deliverables will also be uploaded to the Projects website. mention only the partner's name and not any other personal information. All reports will be kept for 5 years duration.
Usage of cookies	In the cases that in any 5G-ROUTES application (web) the usage of cookies is needed, a related pop-up window informing the user must be present, prompting the user to accept (or not) the conditions under which the personal information is stored.
Project related research data	Any data circulated internally to 5G-ROUTES for research purposes (i.e. data from trials/UCs) must be fully anonymized by the data owner (in this case the data controller) and not relating in any case to personal information as stated in the chapters above.
Personal data related to external stakeholders	Personal data derived partially from the internal 5G-ROUTES lists of external stakeholders and partly from contacts directly received is managed via a GDPR compliant database and management system for the purposes of e-communication.

3.3 Dissemination and communication of the research data

Non-confidential data will be used to prepare public deliverables, publications, advertisement materials, etc., which will be disseminated and communicated to specific stakeholder groups or to a wider public. All publications shall be published in line with the project's DMP and shared through an open research data repository: Zenodo [2] and Open Research Europe [3].

Zenodo is a general-purpose open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE [4] program and allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artifacts. For each submission, a persistent digital object identifier (DOI) is minted, which makes the stored items easily citable. Like Zenodo, Open Research Europe is also an open-access repository which enables researchers to publish any research they wish to share, supporting reproducibility, transparency, and impact. It uses an open research publishing model for publication within days of submission, followed by open invited peer review. Includes citations to all supporting data and materials, enabling re-analyses, replication, and reuse.

Both green and gold open access publications and underlying data must be deposited on the above-mentioned open access repositories. The project agreement only mentions Green open access, but Gold access is also been taken into consideration since it is an increasingly common practice, especially at academic and research

organizations. A machine-readable electronic copy (e.g. the accepted author manuscript or the final PDF) must be deposited in a repository as soon as possible but at the latest upon publication. In the case of the green open access option, authors should add a link to the final version and the accepted author manuscript (AAM) should be used for depositing. This is the final peer-reviewed version of a manuscript, including reviewer comments, but without the lay outting by the publisher.

All public deliverables, after being reviewed and approved by EC, will be shared openly through 5G-ROUTES's website and open research data repositories. All publications shall be published in line with the project's DMP and the project's IP Management Strategy, described below, thus ensuring protection for the project's IP, personal data, etc.

3.4 IP protection and exploitation of the research data and result

During the regular monthly meetings, project partners will discuss the potential of the project's results which may lead to commercial exploitation and therefore decide to protect the data. This will be monitored by the Innovation Manager (ILS), and if cases arise appropriate steps to protect such results for exploitation purposes will be taken. As shown by Figure 1, data underlying such results will not be openly shared. Instead, the data will be archived in the secure internal storage and its corresponding deliverable will only be shared with European Commission during the regular project reviews.

3.5 Processing of Personal Data Approach

This sub-chapter provides a more detailed overview of the use of personal data in the 5G-ROUTES project per WP and Partner. Personal data handling will be done in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR) [5]. Given this, the consortium of 5G-ROUTES is committed to handling potential ethical issues responsibly. All partners will adhere to and respect national regulations and laws and will continue to reflect and refine their own innovation conduct, data processing, ethical principles, and practices.

5G-ROUTES partners are familiar with the ethical requirements associated with research with humans, given their training and previous experience in research and innovation methodology, and are familiar with the sorts of processes needed to meet and exceed these requirements. The consortium will adhere to the following principles:

- All the test subjects, and their legal guardians where applicable, will be informed and given the opportunity to provide their consent to any monitoring and data acquisition process that all the subjects will be strictly volunteers and all tests will receive detailed oral information.
- All stakeholder engagement activities (testing, trials, workshops, etc.) will be conducted with participants that will be able to understand their role in the project, what data is collected, how it is processed, stored, and anonymised and peer reviewed before being used in the project used, for example through publication or as part of system innovation. No covert data collection (undertaken without the consent or knowledge of respondents) will take place.
- No data will be collected without the explicit informed consent of the individuals under observation and their legal guardian where applicable. This involves being open with participants about what they are involving themselves in and ensuring that they have agreed fully to the procedures/research being undertaken by giving their explicit consent.
- Participants will be given information on who will benefit from their participation in the research and what risk or burden they are undertaking by participating.
- The consortium will also provide information about the potential for commercial exploitation of the innovation.
- Participation in these aspects of the 5G-ROUTES project will be fully voluntary and all participants will be given the opportunity to ask questions and receive understandable answers before making decisions about their participation.

- Participants will also have the right to withdraw and terminate their participation in the research at any time and will be reminded about their rights before participation.
- No personal or sensitive data will be centrally stored. In addition, data will be scrambled where possible and abstracted in a way that will not affect the final project outcome.
- No data collected will be sold or used for any purposes other than the current project.
- A data minimisation policy will be adopted at all levels of the project and will be supervised by the Project Coordinator and the Data Protection Officers appointed by each partner. This will ensure that no data which is not strictly necessary to the completion of the current study will be collected.
- Specific measures will be in place to protect the pupils from a breach of privacy/confidentiality and any potential discrimination; In particular their names will not be made public, and their participation will not be communicated to. Any incidental findings will be kept strictly confidential and erased from files under request from the enrolled subject.

3.6 Open Access to Research data proposed approach

Since 2017, all the thematic areas of the H2020 programme have been included in the work programme Open Research Data Pilot (ORD Pilot) which is a flexible pilot on open access to research data and scientific publication in H2020. The pilot considers the need to balance the possibility to make the data open with the protection of scientific information, commercialisation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), privacy concerns, and security, as well as questions of data management and preservation.

The Europe H2020 strategy for a smart, sustainable, and inclusive economy underlines the central role of knowledge and innovation in generating growth. The reason for the creation of the ORD Pilot is that the free access to scientific publications and data should improve the quality of the results on which further research will hopefully be built, encourage collaboration, and avoid duplication of efforts, speed up the entrance of the results into the market and should boost and underline the benefits of public investments in research funded under the H2020 programme also among citizens and society.

From a high-level perspective, open access (OA) consists in providing on-line access to scientific information free of charge to the users to promote the reusability of the data. Within the context of the R&D actions there are two main categories of data that OA addresses: the scientific papers and the research data collected from the experiments conducted in the laboratories. Research data refer to facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning and discussion on project results, examples include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images. The focus is on research data that is available in digital form.

Indeed, the ORD Pilot run by the European Commission applies to the datasets at the basis of scientific publication and to the peer reviewed papers released within the context of the H2020 projects. According to the Budapest declaration (2002) and Berlin Declaration (2003), within the context of ORD Pilot, open access means not only the basic rights to download, save and print a document, but also to copy, distribute, search, link and crawl data. The DMP will be useful to state which type of data will be made available and which restriction may apply to some data. The two main routes to open access, as also presented in Figure 1 above, are the following:

- **Self-archiving / 'green' open access** – the author, or a representative, archives (deposits) the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in an online repository before, at the same time as, or after publication. Some publishers request that open access be granted only after an embargo period has elapsed.
- **Open access publishing / 'gold' open access** - To go through with this option, the author will need to pay for immediate open access. This can either be by publishing in specific open access journals or in so called hybrid open access journals, where one pays for online open. In both cases the author gets immediate access to the high-quality PDF of the manuscript. The publication is usually covered by the Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) license, meaning that the publisher only gets a license to publish the publication but the actual copyright stays with author(s) [6][7][8].

3.7 Data Collection, Archiving & Preservation

All data and information about the data collected from project activities will be analyzed, refined, organized, and stored in a secured data storage accessible to all project partners. To keep track of the collected data, each WP Leader is responsible for defining and describing all collected datasets specific to their individual work package. This shall be done by completing an Excel file called “DMP Registry” (see Table 2) which will be stored on Teamwork, with restrict access only to Consortium partners. More information and the results of the first 14 project months on this process are presented in [Section 4.3](#).

All datasets will be stored in Teamwork file repository. This will be the project's file repository and online collaboration platform during the project lifetime. If there is a need, Teamwork data can remain stored for up to 5 years after the end of the project for final closing activities – after which the data will be permanently removed. The internal structure of the five WP folders will be determined by the Work Package Leader. Project partner who generates the data will be responsible for uploading their datasets to the Teamwork storage. The corresponding WP leader will be responsible to periodically review the WP folders and ensure that the project datasets are archived appropriately and according to DMP procedures.

By the end of the project, the final datasets, public deliverables, and publications will be transferred to the Zenodo and Open Research Europe repositories, which ensures sustainable archiving of the final research data. Items deposited in those repositories will be retained for their lifetime. For Zenodo is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN and has an experimental programme defined for the at least next 20 years (based on Zenodo General Policies [9]).

3.8 FAIR Data Management

FAIR data management relates to the European Commission guidelines on the data being Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reused. 5G-ROUTES relates FAIR data management to naming conventions, contribution to open data research, data identification and searching as well as meta-data provisions and data reusability. The project aims to maximise access to, and re-use of research data generated by the project. At the same time, there are datasets, or parts of datasets, generated in this project that cannot be shared to protect exploitable results and the privacy of voluntary participants in workshops.

3.8.1 Making data findable

5G-ROUTES will use the Zenodo and Open Research Europe repositories as the main tools to make projects' research data findable in accordance with the H2020 Open Access Mandate. A H2020 5G-ROUTES community will be established on both Zenodo and Open Research Europe websites, and the project will upload all our public datasets and deliverables as well as scientific publications to this community. In addition, we will link all projects' uploads to the European Commission Funded Research (OpenAIRE) community for maximum findability. Some more information about making data available over Zenodo is followed.

All uploads will be enriched with standard Zenodo metadata, including Grant Number and Project Acronym. Zenodo provides version control and assigns DOIs to all uploaded elements. The consortium will make use of metadata to describe the data collection and to facilitate the finding and re-use of data. Metadata will have a twofold nature: descriptive, therefore giving information on the data discovery and identification (titles, author, keywords) and administrative outlining when and how data was created, file type and other technical information, and who can access it. Metadata associated with each published data set in Zenodo will by default be as follows:

- Digital Object Identifiers

- Version numbers
- Bibliographic information
- Keywords
- Abstract/description
- Associated project and community
- Associated publications and reports
- Grant information
- Access and licensing info
- Language

Each partner will be responsible for uploading public datasets that they have generated and assign specific keywords relevant to these datasets. Dataset specific keywords must be descriptive to the content of the dataset. In addition, a set of general keywords that should apply to all public datasets, scientific publications, and public deliverables. In the framework of 5G-ROUTES quality plan and control, a series of documents/reports templates have been created to ensure a consistent approach for all 5G-ROUTES data and their versions.

Zenodo supports DOI versioning [10], which allows users to update datasets after they have been made public and researchers to easily cite either specific versions of a record or to cite, via a top-level DOI, all the versions of a record. DOI stands for "Digital Object Identifier", meaning a "digital identifier of an object". As outlined in the DOI handbook [11]:

- The DOI syntax is made up of a DOI prefix and a DOI suffix separated by a forward slash. The DOI prefix is composed of a directory indicator followed by a registrant code.
 - The directory indicator is always "10".
 - The registrant code is a unique string assigned to a registrant (i.e. 5072).
 - The directory indicator and the registrant code are separated by a dot ".".
- The DOI suffix consists of a character string of any length chosen by the registrant. Each suffix shall be unique to the prefix element that precedes it. The unique suffix can be a sequential number, or it might incorporate an identifier generated from or based on another system used by the registrant (i.e. ISAN [12], ISBN [13], ISRC [14], ISSN [15], ISTC [16], etc.)

Zenodo registers one DOI per version of the dataset, and in addition one Concept DOI is registered. The Concept DOI represents all versions of a record, and semantically link all the per-version DOIs.

As an example, DOI versioning of a dataset that is released in several versions can look like this:

- v1.0: 10.5072/zenodo.123
- v2.0: 10.5072/zenodo.321
- Concept (all versions): 10.5072/zenodo.122

The first two DOIs for versions v1.0 and v.2.0 represent the specific versions of the dataset, while the Concept (the last DOI) represents all the versions of the dataset package, i.e. the concept of the dataset and the ensemble of versions. They are referred to as Version DOIs and Concept DOIs, but in fact they are both normal DOIs.

This does not, however, mean that a new DOI will be assigned each time the metadata of the dataset is edited (i.e. change the title of a file or dataset). A new DOI version will only be created if one updates the actual files that have been uploaded.

Figure 2: DOIs for Research Data [17]

The H2020 Open Access Mandate aims to make research data generated by H2020 projects accessible with as few restrictions as possible, but also accept protection of personal or sensitive data due to privacy concerns and/or commercial or security reasons. All public datasets, scientific publications and deliverables will be uploaded to Zenodo and made openly available, free of charge. Publications and underlying data sets will be linked through use of persistent identifiers (DOI versioning). Datasets and publications which are "confidential" will not be shared due to privacy concerns or potential for commercial exploitation. If such cases arise during the project, this will be informed in the final version of the DMP.

Metadata including licenses for individual data records as well as record collections will be harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API. The data will be available through Zenodo and hence accessible using any web browsing application. The list of expected datasets in Section 4.3 constitutes the first version of dataset description and we recognise that it will develop and grow as the project evolves. In addition, some information concerning the datasets might remain unknown at this time, for example size of the datasets. An updated version of this list will be provided at the end of the project.

3.8.2 Making data accessible

This initial DMP is adjusted and serves 5G-ROUTES' aims to contribute data to the open research pilot. Data sets which are candidates for sharing will be checked to ensure that:

- They are not confidential, that they do not include personal or commercially sensitive information.
- Permission from the relevant stakeholders and/or data subjects has been obtained. Sharing the data does not damage exploitation or IP protection prospects, in alignment with processes set in Innovation, IPR & Data Management.

Consequently, datasets will be revised by the 5G-ROUTES's Project Coordinator in collaboration with the Innovation Manager, WP Leaders and the DPO assigned by each Partner ([Annex 2](#)); and must be endorsed before becoming candidates for contribution to the open research pilot. These parties and the originating consortium partner(s) will then agree licensing (for example creative commons or public domain). Following in principle

approval, 5G-ROUTES will make the datasets accessible through appropriate open access repositories, following the guidelines of the Grant Agreement.

The approval of the availability of data in an open approach will need to be sent to the project coordinator from the actual data owners via email. For this, a consent that the data can be distributed outside the consortium must be included in the approval email to the project coordinator. The following information should be included:

- Data Processor
- Description of data (what the data include)
- Data filenames and version
- Consent to publish data outside the 5G-ROUTES consortium

The following repository systems is used and will be used in 5G-ROUTES Project:

- **Teamwork:** Already mentioned in Section 3.7. It will be used as the Project main file repository and documentation/data exchange among consortium partners. It also serves as centralized access to the relevant information and documents of importance to monitor the progresses in the project and to promote communication between partners, revisions of documents and their repository. Teamwork will be the main server where all project data will be shared and exchanged between the different beneficiaries. Teamwork is also used for editing the DMP Registry tables by the WP Leaders / Consortium Partners online. Access is restricted to the consortium members. Teamwork is considered as GDPR Compliant².
- **Zenodo & Open Research Europe:** All scientific publications, including public deliverables and public parts of underlying datasets will be uploaded to the H2020 5G-ROUTES Community in addition to the European Commission Funded Research (OpenAIRE) Community in Zenodo. Zenodo is a "catch-all" open research data repository which gathers research data across all disciplinary fields. Open Research Europe enables researchers to publish any research they wish to share, supporting reproducibility, transparency, and impact. Uses an open research publishing model: publication within days of submission, followed by open invited peer review. Includes citations to all supporting data and materials, enabling reanalysis, replication, and reuse.

3.8.3 Data interoperability

Data interoperability is considered only for internal purposes of 5G-ROUTES and includes data re-use, interchanges, and general utilisation. For data interoperability outside the consortium, 5G-ROUTES will follow IPR rules to ensure no 5G-ROUTES foreground is released. More details on data sharing outside the consortium as far as IPs are related are provided in [Section 4](#) of this report.

As far as filename conventions are concerned to maximize data interoperability, the consortium will do their best effort to comply with commonly used filenames such as .XML, .XLS(X), etc. Apart from the commonly used standards (relating to commonly used filenames), 5G-ROUTES will investigate the possibility to follow other (internationally recognized) standards for both actual data and software produced.

5G-ROUTES project aims to collect and document the data in a standardized way to ensure the datasets would be easy to understand, reuse and interoperate among different parties who are interested in utilizing them. Standard technical terminology will also be used to facilitate inter-disciplinary interoperability. Data and metadata vocabularies used to make data interoperable are standard vocabularies or OAI-PMH and SWORD (Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit).

² Teamwork GDPR Compliance: <https://www.teamwork.com/legal/gdpr/>

Zenodo uses JSON schema as the internal representation of metadata and offers export to other formats such as DublinCore (Dublin Core Metadata Element Set) [18], MARCXML (MARC 21 XML Schema) [19], BibTeX [20], Citation Style Language (CSL) [21], DataCite Metadata Schema [22] and export to Mendeley [23]. The data record metadata will utilise the vocabularies applied by Zenodo. For certain terms, these refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g.: license (Open Definition), funders (FundRef) and grants (OpenAIRE). Reference to any external metadata is done with a resolvable URL.

3.8.4 Data Reusability of Existing and Non-Existing Data

Existing data in the concept of 5G-ROUTES project will be considered data previously existing and not created by the project's activities. The consortium will make sure the data are correctly and securely stored in a convenient and secure server to enable easy access outside the consortium but at the same time control access of users. This will be achieved through the 5G-ROUTES's cloud server.

The reuse of data is a key component in FAIR. It ensures that data can be reused for purposes other than it was initially created for. At this stage, it is not clear what licensing models need to be applied for the various data products produced in 5G-ROUTES. Application of licenses will be assessed on a case-by-basis in close collaboration with the Coordinator, Innovation Manager and partners concerned.

The 5G-ROUTES project will enable third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate (free of charge for any user) for all public data sets, and regulate this by using Creative Commons Attribution Licenses. Creative Commons licenses (CC) are tools to grant copyright permissions to creative work. As a default, the CC-BY-SA [24] license will be applied for public 5G-ROUTES data. This license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon one's work even for commercial purposes, if they credit the author and license their new creations under the identical terms. This license is often compared to "copyleft", free and open-source software licenses. With this license all new work based on 5G-ROUTES data and results will carry the same license, so any derivatives will also allow commercial use. This does not preclude the use of less restrictive licenses as CC-BY or more restrictive licenses as CC-BY-NC, which does not allow commercial usage.

3.8.5 Longevity of the 5G-ROUTES research datasets

For data published in scientific journals, the underlying data will be made available no later than by journal publication. The data will be linked to the publication. Data associated with public deliverables will be shared once the deliverable has been approved and accepted by the EC. Other public datasets not directly linked to a scientific publication or deliverable will be made available upon assessment by the consortium and ready for publishing in the final month of the project, at the latest.

Open data can be reused in accordance with the Creative Commons licenses. Data classified as confidential will as default is not reusable due to privacy concerns. The public data will remain reusable via Zenodo for at least 20 years. This is currently the lifetime stated by the host laboratory CERN. If Zenodo must close their operations, they have provided a guarantee that they will migrate all content (including metadata) to other suitable repositories.

Confidential data will be deleted at the end of the project. In case permission is given by the party providing and owning the data, some non-anonymous data will be kept for a maximum of 5 years after the contractual end date of the project. The additional 4 months is to keep the underlying datasets available to allow the completion of any scientific publications being prepared towards the end of the project. An exemption are materials (i.e. pictures, videos) that are used for communication purposes. Such data will be kept for up 5 years after the end of the project to comply with the EC contractual obligation to continue dissemination and exploitation activities after the project ends.

4 Data Lifecycle and Related Procedures

This chapter explains the whole data life cycle that will be taking place in the 5G-ROUTES project. 5G-ROUTES considers the different stages at which data is created, managed, or utilised during the whole project lifecycle.

Figure 3: 5G-ROUTES Data Lifecycle

The previous Figure 3 indicates the 5G-ROUTES data lifecycle in a typical flow with several processes/stages as also listed and explained below.

- **Data Creation and Collection:** This stage includes the data creation and/or collection based on projects' activities and the various data provided by the trials, the project reports (i.e. deliverables) as well as other documents or spreadsheets. This includes the creation of the data (by the respective owner) and the collection in a structured and format manner, and layouts to enable their processing by the other project components or partners.
- **Data Processing and Analysis:** This stage is related to the actual data processing by the various data processors. Processors are the partners that will have access to the data based on project needs and expected outcomes. During this stage we need to ensure that the processors can perform data processing in a concise approach, including data verification, organization, transformation, integration, and extraction for the intended use, to fulfil the project needs. Data analysis includes all the actions and methodology performed on the actual data that describes existing facts, identify outlines, develop data clarifications, etc.
- **Data Publication and Utilisation:** This stage includes the publication of data, meaning the need to share data openly to the public. Moreover, utilization includes the steps towards data sharing, internally to projects' Consortium. Controlling mechanisms need to be in place to ensure that the data is shared with the appropriate protection of proprietary data as well as the data integrity itself. Finally, this stage is closely linked with the next stage (data storage and archiving) as far as metadata is related to ensure data searchability.
- **Data Storage, Archiving and Reuse:** The storage and archiving stage is critical as it is related to the data access, storage, sharing, archiving and re-usage. This should also involve actions to ensure accidental data loss or deletion, data corruption or even unauthorized access to the data. Data storage and archiving is also strongly linked to data reusability that is also part of the FAIR data treatment.

In each of the above-mentioned steps, specific metrics have been identified to be followed related to the data management along with controls (summarised into the data management report template - Table below). This template will be used at various project stages to control data management compliancy.

Table 3: Data Management Report Template

Performance Indicator	Verification Method	Target	Compliance
Data Creation and Collection			
Data format	Compliance with existing standards of data exchange	.XLS, .XML, .DOC, etc.	[Y/N]
Availability and Readability	Whole set of data available, non-corrupted, and collected	Fully accessibility	[Y/N]
Fit for Use	Data follow data compliancy for proper processing and review	Fully usable by intended beneficiary	[Y/N]
Consistency and Completeness	Data are consistent and complete for the intended purpose	Fully information included	[Y/N]
Relation	Data follow a precise relation to their purpose	Fully purpose precision	[Y/N]
Data Processing and Analysis			
Data logic	Data can be processed following a concise logic and approach	New and processed data fully follow precise data logic	[Y/N]
Organization and Utility	Data under processing to have suitable content organization	Fully organized data	[Y/N]
Validation	Ensuring that the processed data are correct and relevant	Fully validated and relevant data	[Y/N]
Aggregation	In case multiple data needs to be aggregated, ensure that this process is done in a concise approach	Fully aggregate-able data	[Y/N]
Transformation	Transformation of data to the proper format(s) for processing	Capability of data for transformation (if needed)	[Y/N]
Calibration	Calibration of data if required	Data properly calibrated	[Y/N]
Data Publication and Utilization			
Means-independent	Transferring of the data in a means-independent approach	Fully means independent transferability	[Y/N]
Security	Data stored in a secure location (i.e. database, server)	Accessing controls are provided along with detailed storage information	[Y/N]
Data Storage, Archiving and Reuse			
Up to date	Ensuring that the stored data are up to date and no later version exists	Fully updated	[Y/N]
Metadata	Existence of metadata in stored files	Relevant metadata have been included into the archive per dataset	[Y/N]
Security	Access control provided along with storing information (Project cloud server is considered as safe enough)	Access controls (Transport Layer Security protocol	[Y/N]

Performance Indicator	Verification Method	Target	Compliance
		preferable) and detailed storage information	
Expiration	Properly set of date (or duration) after which the data will be deleted	Expiration date properly setup	[Y/N]

4.1 Roles and Responsibilities Regarding the Data Management Plan

WP5 and, Task 5.3 is responsible for the data management lifecycle monitoring for all datasets to be collected, processed, or generated by the project. To ensure compliance with data management decisions as they relate to the DMP, the following roles and responsibilities are applying in 5G-ROUTES.

- **5G-ROUTES DPO:** for the overall 5G-ROUTES project activities, the Project coordinator (ERICSSON) is considered as the project's DPO which will be available to assist - if needed - in decision-making as 5GROUTES is developed to identify potential risks, mitigation solutions and support compliance. In the case of personal data processing, Project coordinator will serve as the project's DPO assisted by the DPO point of contact of each of the consortium's members, to manage such data.
- **WP Leaders:** are considered responsible for adhering to the specifications mentioned above, and the monitoring and handling of the data generated by each participant in the WP they are leading.
- **Appointed Data Protection Officer (DPO) per partner:** Following and completing an official appointment template provided by the Project ([Annex 1](#)), each partner has assigned a dedicated DPO for the project ([Annex 2](#)). Each DPO, along with the personnel of each organisation (assigned and working on the project) are considered responsible for the management of the project's collected data within their organisation. They should also ensure that personnel working on the project have read the data management plan and apply/exercise all the principles as described in the 5G-ROUTES DMP (this document).
- **Data Processors:** partner(s) working with the data produced by the project. Data processors have the responsibility of complying with the specifics of the 5G-ROUTES Data Management plan, as well as to the related Ethics requirements and GDPR policies ([Chapter 3.2](#)).
- **Innovation Manager:** EBOS as the project's Innovation Manager acts as the main advisor on any data related issue during the project lifecycle. It is also the responsible partner for the setup of the Projects' Data Management Plan and procedures to be followed.

4.2 DMP Registry Live Document

In this chapter we define the data collection concepts and data purposes as they relate to the 5G-ROUTES project work breakdown structure. After consultation with the 5G-ROUTES WP leaders we have described the following items:

- Lead Partner
- Owner of the data
- Data Origin
- Data Type(s)
- Purpose of collecting
- Data Processing Activities
- Data Format
- Quantity (Approximated Data Size)
- Public / Confidential

- Storage Location
- Which partner will use the data / has access to it?

To keep track on the information of the collected data, each WP Leader is responsible for defining and describing information about collected datasets specific to their individual work package. This shall be done by completing an Excel file called “DMP Registry” which is stored on Teamwork, with restrict access only to Consortium partners. As shown in the table below DMP Registry contains both qualitative and quantitative description of the project datasets.

Table 4: DMP Registry Template

Lead Partner (Data Processor)	Name of the lead partner responsible for dataset generation, collection, processing.
Owner of the data	Who is the owner of the data
Data Origin	Description of the origin of the data (lab tests, computer simulation,
Data Type(s)	Type of data contained in the dataset e.g. narrative texts, numbers, images, audio files, video files, internal/external reports, KPIs, statistics, figures, questionnaires, check lists, user stories.
Purpose of collecting	The purpose of the data collection/generation?
Data Processing Activities	Actions performed on those data (share, edit, use for statistics, etc.)
Data Format	Data format could be: .doc/.docx, .xls/.xlsx, .pdf, .ppt/.pptx etc.
Quantity (Approximated Data Size)	Approximate size of dataset in Mb/Gb and number of files
Public / Confidential to the Consortium	Public data: made available to other researchers through the EC’s repositories or through the project. Confidential to the consortium: data that cannot be exposed in public (including information included in confidential deliverables)
Personal Data (Yes/No)	Mark Yes or No if the collected data includes personal information
Storage Location	Where is data stored on the server i.e. name of the server + path.
Data Storage Duration	The duration the data will be stored (i.e. project duration or more, and why)
Which partner will use the data / has access to it?	Who has access to the data? And what type of access is it, i.e. viewing, editing, etc.

This DMP Registry file is a "living document" meaning that it will remain online and always accessible only by the Consortium partners. Teamwork is considered as GDPR Compliant, but in any case for the project purposes, no personal data or any other raw data collected, are stored in this DMP Registry file. The purpose of this "living document" is to be updated constantly with what type of data each partner is collecting (but not to host the data as such). On the provided DMP Registry file, there is a column called “Data Storage Location”, where each partner indicates where the actual data are stored (i.e. Teamwork, database, etc.). A snapshot of the existing DMP Registry file is presented in the figure below.

Updates over project Lifecycle											
	M1-M3	M4-M6	M7-M9	M10-M12	M13-M15	M16-M18	M19-M21	M22-M24	M25-M27	M28-M30	M31-M33
	Sept 2020 - Nov 2020	Dec 2020 - Feb 2021	Mar 2021 - May 2021	Jun 2021 - Aug 2021	Sept 2021 - Nov 2021	Dec 2021 - Feb 2022	Mar 2022 - May 2022	Jun 2022 - Aug 2022	Sept 2022 - Nov 2022	Dec 2022 - Feb 2023	Mar 2023 - May 2023
EEE	√	√	√	√	√						
ADS	√	√	√	√	√						
ADSF	√	√	√								
PV	√	√	√								
ATOS	√	√	√	√	√						
BRA	√	√	√								
CTTC	√	√	√	√	√						
EBOS	√	√	√	√	√						
EVR	√	√	√								
ENIDE	√	√	√	√							
CERTH	√	√	√	√	√						
ILS	√	√	√	√	√						
VED	√	√	√		√						
IQU	√	√	√	√	√						
LMT	√	√	√	√	√						
SWA	√	√	√	√	√						
TTTU	√	√	√	√	√						
VTT	√	√	√	√							
TELIA	√	√	√		√						
UNITI	√	√	√		√						
VEDIA	√	√	√	√							
WINGS	√	√	√		√						
Teamwork file log	Link to the file										

Figure 4: Snapshot of the DMP Registry File

As already mentioned, to keep track of the collected data, each WP Leader is responsible for defining and describing all collected datasets specific to their individual work package. It is identified that there will be predefined updates on the DMP Registry file every 3 months (after collaboration with the partners participated in their WP), for the entire projects’ lifetime. The DMP of course it is mandatory to be updated over the course of the project whenever significant changes arise, such as (but not limited to):

- New data collected (i.e. trials period)
- Changes in consortium policies (i.e. new innovation potential)
- Changes in consortium composition and external factors (i.e. a new consortium member is joining or an old members is leaving).
- In time with the periodic evaluation/assessment of the project.

Data management and the updates of DMP Registry will be continuously monitored by EBOS, as part of the work in WP5. Moreover, to keep history on changes performed in the DMP Registry file, each version of this document (every 3 months) is it exported and securely stored in the project repository (Teamwork).

4.3 Data Collected Information per WP (M14)

At the time of preparing this deliverable Work Package leaders have updated the DMP Registry file based on the datasets that are expected to be collected in their work packages by M14 and presented in the following tables in a WP/Partner structure. “N/A” appeared in the following Tables means that the requested information is not available in the moment.

Table 5: WP1 Data Management Plan

WP1 Requirements analysis, use cases and preparation for CAM trials												
Lead Partner (Data Processor)	Owner of the data	Data Origin	Data Type	Purpose of collecting	Data Processing Activities	Data Format	Quantity	Public / Confidential to the consortium	Personal Data (Yes/No)	Data Storage Location	Data Storage Duration	Which partner will use the data / has access to it?
ADS	ADS and use case owner	Use cases analysis	Satellite connectivity KPIs	Project needs	N/A	.doc	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners
BRA	BRA, ADSF, VTT	Use cases analysis	Use cases KPIs and requirements, Deliverable 1.1 and 1.7 contributions	Use case needs and objectives	N/A	.doc	N/A	Public	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners
EBOS	UC Leaders	Requirements for the tenant portal	N/A	Project needs	N/A	.doc	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners
LMT	LMT	Gathered data about 5G network architecture & functionalities, public sources for elaboration of WP1 deliverables.	Different 5G network and UCs data, analysis, etc. public information required for elaboration of D1.3, D1.4, D1.10 and partners WP1 Deliverables.	Project needs	N/A	.doc, .xls, graphs, images	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners

WP1 Requirements analysis, use cases and preparation for CAM trials												
VTT	All UC participants	data collected from partners and public sources for use cases definition	data and KPIs regarding use cases	use cases and test framework specification	N/A	Text	n/a	public	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners
WINGS	All UC participants	Project partners	Use Case 5.2 requirements	To identify all the requirements and KPIs that have to be met for use case 5.2	Data Analysis	Text	Specific KPI values	Public	No	Teamwork	Project duration + longer as part of public deliverables	All project partners & external readers of deliverables

Table 6: WP2 Data Management Plan

WP2 Development of technological enablers for CAM trials												
Lead Partner (Data Processor)	Owner of the data	Data Origin	Data Type	Purpose of collecting	Data Processing Activities	Data Format	Quantity	Public / Confidential to the consortium	Personal Data (Yes/No)	Data Storage Location	Data Storage Duration	Which partner will use the data / has access to it?
ATOS	ATOS	Enabler's capabilities	Technical requirements	Integration	N/A	N/A	N/A	Public	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Enablers leaders
CTTC	CTTC	Technological enablers, CTTC 5G testbed	KPIs	Project needs	N/A	N/A	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	UCs leaders of KPI measurements from the testbed)
EBOS	UC Leaders	CAM use cases & Lab/field trials	Technical specifications UML diagrams KPI calculations	As part of the implementation of the tenant web portal	Storing, filtering and presentation	.XML .XLS	Some thousands of records	Public	No	Tenant portal	Project duration	CAM use cases and rest of the partners will have view access

WP2 Development of technological enablers for CAM trials

			and representation									
CERTH	N/A	Open Datasets	Mobility Traces and Spatial Data for Open Street Maps	Implementation and integrations of the enablers developed by CERTH	Cleaned and transformed to be used as input to AI algorithms	.csv	Some Hundreds of thousands of records (approx. 10 GB)	Public	No	CERTH Premises and Teamwork	Project duration	CERTH
IQU	IQU	CTTC testbed, innovation of technological enablers	KPIs, Requirements	Project needs	N/A	N/A	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners
TTU	TTU	Simulated data for V2X positioning task 2.3 based on 5G 3GPP release 16 and beyond	Test vectors of positioning reference signal (PRS signals) from 5G	Project needs to develop algorithms for positioning	processing to calculate vehicle coordinates and performance evaluation of the algorithms	CSV, mat files, .png	PRS signal itself is several bytes but for the algorithms we need large data set for training	Both	N/A	TTU and Teamwork	Project duration	CTTC for positioning service placement, and other partners who will need the data
VTT	VTT	data collected during position measurement campaigns	location	development of enablers and improvement of	algorithm development	N/A	N/A	Both	No (data only collected for testing purposes)	VTT and Teamwork	Project duration	VTT and use case participants

WP2 Development of technological enablers for CAM trials												
				position accuracy								
WINGS	Data is not stored, hence no owner.	Collecting data from OBU, RSU, smartphones and various sensors for the AI/ML developed in T2.2 and UC5.2	User/vehicle location, vehicle attributes (speed, revs, temperature), camera feed & pics	Location is needed to identify users about to change networks (roaming) and to initiate resource pre-allocation at the visiting network. Sensor data is needed as input to the AI/ML algorithm to perform slice negotiation and risk assessment	data fusion & analytics processing, license plate recognition from camera pictures	All data are transmitted in text/CSV format.	depends on number of users per trial. Data is transmitted in a timescale below 1 sec.	Confidential	No	Teamwork and WINGS Cloud/Edge server * (Data is only stored for post-processing and KPI calculations. Once the necessary metrics are calculated detailed data are deleted. No permanent storage of data.	2-4 weeks	WINGS. Data encryption during transmission and anonymization techniques will be applied

Table 7: WP3 Data Management Plan

WP3 5G infrastructure setup and operational readiness												
CTTC	EDI	Use Case required, racetrack	Point Cloud	Ground Truth localization	UC1.1, UC1.2, UC2.2, T3.2	.pcd	1	Confidential	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners

WP3 5G infrastructure setup and operational readiness

EBOS	EDI	Use Case required, Bikernieku racetrack	Radar Data	Safety fallback	UC1.1, UC1.2, UC2.2, T3.2	candump	1	public	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners
EVR	CTTC	CTTC 5G testbed	KPIs	Project needs	N/A	N/A	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners
ENIDE	EBOS	Lab trials data	row data	As part of the execution of the tenant web portal	Storing, filtering and presentation	.XML .XLS	Some thousands of records	Public	No	Teamwork and Tenant portal	Project duration	Consortium partners
SWA	IQU	CTTC testbed	KPIs	Project needs	N/A	N/A	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners
TTU	LMT, TELIA	5G SA Core and UCs vehicle data - racetrack, Bikernieki, cross border trials Valka-Valga	5G network infrastructure data (MEC, Orchestration, metrics, KPIs, etc.), vehicle data & KPIs	Project needs	5G network deployment at cross border Valka-Valga and CAM UCs: UC1.1., UC1.2, UC1.3, UC2.1, UC3.1, UC3.2.	N/A	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners
VTT	City of Valga/ SWA	Data acquired from devices installed in specific locations to develop the trials	Traffic Light Data, Sensors Data, KPI's	Base for C-ITS services	Elaboration of C-ITS messages	ETSI standards for C-ITS (in output), proprietary formats (in input)	Real time data per two intersections	Confidential	No	Teamwork	Raw data - 1-week, Aggregated KPIs - Project duration	Consortium partners
TELIA	TTU	TTU 5G-IoT testbed and TTU 5G D2D	Data from OBD dongles/sen	Use case 3.2 and other	Developing machine learning	REST, JSON (JavaScript Object	Thousands of records	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners

WP3 5G infrastructure setup and operational readiness												
		SideLink testbed	sors (monitor vehicles' condition).	Project needs	algorithms for UC3.2	Notation) and MQTT.						

Table 8: WP4 Data Management Plan

WP4 5G infrastructure setup and operational readiness												
Lead Partner (Data Processor)	Owner of the data	Data Origin	Data Type	Purpose of collecting	Data Processing Activities	Data Format	Quantity	Public / Confidential to the consortium	Personal Data (Yes/No)	Data Storage Location	Data Storage Duration	Which partner will use the data / has access to it?
ADS	ADS and use case owner	Use cases analysis	Satellite connectivity KPIs	Project needs	N/A	mainly .doc	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners
CTTC	CTTC	CTTC 5G testbed	KPIs	Project needs	N/A	N/A	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners
EBOS	EBOS	CAM use cases & field trials	row data	As part of the execution of the tenant web portal	Storing, filtering and presentation	.XML .XLS	Some thousands of records	Public	No	Teamwork and Tenant portal	Project duration	Consortium partners
CERTH	CERTH, VEDECOM	UC3.3 Large-scale pilot - User evaluation tests	User evaluation Questionnaires: System Usability Survey (SUS), User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ), Automation Trust Index (SATI),	User acceptance and user experience assessment of UC3.3	Excel	.doc, .xls)	depending on no of users recruited	Both	No	Teamwork, User profile in hard copies only at CERTH	Project duration	Consortium partners

WP4 5G infrastructure setup and operational readiness												
			Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)									
IQU	IQU	CTTC testbed	KPIs	Project needs	N/A	N/A	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners
LMT	LMT, TELIA, EEE	Large-scale cross-border field trials Valka-Valga	5G network infrastructure data (MEC, Orchestration, metrics, KPIs, etc.), CAM vehicle data & KPIs from UCs	To perform large scale cross-border trials by validating 5G functionalities over 3GPP R.16 and R.17.	TBC	N/A	TBC	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners
PV	PV	Sensors	Images and 3D point cloud	To perform railway infrastructure monitoring	Data collection, post processing, long term storage and visualisation	Video and image files, data tables	N/A	Confidential	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners
SWA	City of Valga/ SWA	UC 2.1 deployment of the lab trial and large-trial	Evaluation of performance of the CCAM systems based on 5G	Assessment of the continuity of the service base	Elaboration and analysis of the C-ITS messages	ETSI standards for C-ITS (in output), proprietary	Real time data per two	Confidential	No	Teamwork	Raw data - 1-week, Aggregated KPIs -	Consortium partners

WP4 5G infrastructure setup and operational readiness												
			and AI (Traffic Light Data, Sensors Data)	on 5G to provide enhanced CCAM functionalities and services for VRU's and autonomous "drivers"		formats (input)	intersections				Project duration	
TTU	TTU	TTU 5G-IoT testbed and TTU 5G D2D SideLink testbed	Data from OBD dongles/sensors (monitor vehicles' condition).	Use case 3.2 and other Project needs (use cases)	Developing machine learning algorithms for UC3.2	REST, JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) and MQTT.	Thousands of records	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners
VTT	VTT	vehicles, applications on MEC and cloud For vehicles: only controlled tests; for VRUs and other road users: only metadata are stored; for video in UC1.3: data is only streamed, and not stored	vehicle data, message data, data for KPIs	KPI calculation	calculation of KPIs	CSV files (format in D2.7)	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork and Tenant portal	Project duration	Consortium partners
VEDIA	Vedia	VCU (Vedia IoT gateway)	GNSS positioning including RTK (Real	IoT mMTC testing, supply chain	Vedia CaaS collects sample data, which	NMEA184	5 IoT devices + 5-20 mobile	Confidential	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners

WP4 5G infrastructure setup and operational readiness												
			time kinematics) assistant data	transparenc y/ETA	is used for mMTC simulation tests		phones + simulation for 1 million devices					
WINGS	WINGS	5G testbeds, networks and components participating in the test and field trials for the WINGS led use case (UC5.2)	Network and application-level measurements/KPIs such as throughput, latency, reliability, etc.	Performanc e evaluation of the network and developed applications	Data analytics & post processing	textual/CSV format	unknown (dependi ng on number and duration of tests/field trials	Public	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners

Table 9: WP5 Data Management Plan

WP5 Commercialisation, Innovation management and standardisation												
Lead Partner (Data Processor)	Owner of the data	Data Origin	Data Type	Purpose of collecting	Data Processing Activities	Data Format	Quantity	Public / Confidential to the consortium	Personal Data (Yes/No)	Data Storage Location	Data Storage Duration	Which partner will use the data / has access to it?
BRA	BRA	Brainstorm market and commercializat ion strategy analysis	Documentati on, deliverable contribution	Analysis of market strategy	N/A	.doc	N/A	Public	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium partners
CTTC	CTTC	CTTC 5G testbed, innovation of technological enablers, IPRs / patent, contribution to	KPIs, scientific publications, patent, other	Project needs	N/A	N/A	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium or public

WP5 Commercialisation, Innovation management and standardisation												
		standardization activities										
EBOS	EBOS	IPRs and Patent Data management plan	publications, patents, collection of project data management	Project needs	Data collection, long term storage	.doc, .xls	N/A	Both	Yes	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium or public (depends on data type)
CERTH	CERTH	MAMCA Forms, Interviews, Focus Groups	Doc, Excel	MAMCA Analysis, CBA input	AHP, Excel (statistical analysis)	Excel	N/A	Confidential	No	CERTH, Teamwork	Project duration	WP5 Partners
ILS	ILS	commercialization/innovation/patenting questionnaires, working groups	Doc, Excel	input to D5.1/D5.2	N/A	Excel	N/A	Confidential	No	ILS, Teamwork	Project duration	WP5 Partners
IQU	IQU	CTTC testbed, innovation of technological enablers	KPIs, scientific publications	Project needs	N/A	N/A	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium or public (depends on data type)
LMT	LMT	Development of business models and commercialization analysis based on outcomes from 5G network deployment at Valka-Valga, UCs, cross-border trials, race track "Bikernieki".	Various.	Both: a) for projects needs and Deliverables ; b) for analysing 5G network and CAM solutions for deployment & commercialization needs.	Quantitative and qualitative analysis of information	Majority - .doc, .xls, but could be other in other formats.	N/A	Both	Both. Consent will be asked during data collection	LMT, Teamwork	Depends on type of data: some data during Project duration, other part - permanent	Depends on type of data.

WP5 Commercialisation, Innovation management and standardisation												
SWA	City of Valga/ SWA	Development of business models and commercialization analysis according to UC 2.1 outcomes	Publications, reports	Inputs to WP5 Deliverables	Quantitative and qualitative analysis of information	.doc, .xls	According to the information acquired	Both	No	Teamwork	Raw data - 1-week, Aggregated KPIs - Project duration	Consortium Partners
WINGS	WINGS	Test and field trial results, cost items, bibliography, user acceptance questionnaire.	Cost of equipment purchased, cost of development & deployment, cost of maintenance and support, bibliographic data on market penetration, metrics from tests/trials regarding performance improvement and developed solution results. Questionnaire responses.	Perform an impact assessment for the WINGS developed solution, as well as a market and business plan for further exploitation, market impact, innovation potentials, etc.	Data analytics and post-processing	various	N/A	Confidential	N/A	WINGS	Permanent	WINGS

Table 10: WP6 Data Management Plan

WP6 Dissemination, Communication and scale-up												
Lead Partner (Data Processor)	Owner of the data	Data Origin	Data Type	Purpose of collecting	Data Processing Activities	Data Format	Quantity	Public / Confidential to the consortium	Personal Data (Yes/No)	Data Storage Location	Data Storage Duration	Which partner will use the data / has access to it?
ATOS	ATOS	Contributions to 5GPPP WGs	collaboration actions 5GPPP	keep track and coordinate activities around 5gppp	N/A	shared excel file	N/A	Confidential	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium or public
CTTC	CTTC	CTTC contribution to dissemination activities	dissemination related, meeting participants, etc.	Project needs	N/A	N/A	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium or public
EBOS	EBOS	EBOS contribution to dissemination	articles, social media posts	project dissemination activities	published on social media	emails, photos	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium or public
ENIDE	ENIDE	ENIDE contribution to dissemination	social media posts, presentations	Dissemination activities	N/A	N/A	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium or public
IQU	IQU	IQU contribution to dissemination activities	dissemination related, meeting participants, etc.	Project needs	N/A	N/A	N/A	Both	N/A	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium or public
LMT	LMT	LMT contribution to dissemination activities	Presentations, participants' lists of the meetings, events, articles,	For project dissemination activities	N/A	Different formats	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium or public

WP6 Dissemination, Communication and scale-up												
			social media posts.									
SWA	SWA	Contribution to dissemination and papers elaboration	meetings, events, articles, social media posts.	Project dissemination activities	N/A	N/A	N/A	Both	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium or public
TTU	TTU	TTU's contribution to dissemination activities (e.g. scientific publications, white papers, tutorials and PhD schools)	Presentations, papers, lectures notes, list of participants, etc.	Dissemination and evaluation of dissemination activities	tbc	MS PowerPoint, Word, etc.	N/A	Both	N/A	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium or public
VTT	VTT	contributions to dissemination and exploitation	dissemination related	dissemination	n/a	dissemination formats	N/A	dissemination : public exploitation: both	N/A	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium or public

Table 11: WP7 Data Management Plan

WP7 Project Management												
Lead Partner (Data Processor)	Owner of the data	Data Origin	Data Type	Purpose of collecting	Data Processing Activities	Data Format	Quantity	Public / Confidential to the consortium	Personal Data (Yes/No)	Data Storage Location	Data Storage Duration	Which partner will use the data / has access to it?
EBOS	EBOS	Official deliverables	Quality review information	Quality review	Storage	.doc .xls	N/A	Both	Yes	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium Partners
ENIDE	ENIDE	Official deliverables	Quality review information	Quality review process	N/A	Documents	N/A	Confidential	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium Partners

WP7 Project Management												
LMT	LMT	Employment contracts etc.	Personal data of LMT employees, etc.	For management needs	Storage	Documents	N/A	Confidential	Yes	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium Partners
SWA	SWA	WP7 work and internal financial statements	N/A	For management needs	N/A	documents	N/A	Confidential	No	Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium Partners
TTU	TTU	Work contracts etc.	Personal data of employees and PhD students	Project management needs	Storage	Text	N/A	Confidential		Teamwork	Project duration	Consortium Partners

4.3.1 Data Overview

Looking deeper into the data information collected by the partners in the DMP Registry, as presented in the Tables above, we are highlighting the following:

- Teamwork is the main storage location for documents and confidential (to the consortium) data, including dissemination material, deliverables, market analysis info, contact information and other project documentation.
- Data collected during trials execution:
 - Will be stored in Teamwork file repository and will be finally transmitted in a database (part of the Tenant Web Portal), located in the project's git cloud environment.
 - Contains both public (i.e. 5G network data) and confidential (i.e. traffic light or sensors data) to the consortium data
 - Not contains any personal information.
 - Does not need any special treatment – for example anonymization.
 - As has been decided between the Consortium partners, by the end of the project, the final datasets, public deliverables, and other public data can be shared in Zenodo and Open Research Europe.
- Personal data collected during webinars, events, exploitation activities, or even information like Employment contracts are securely store in Teamwork with limited access to the consortium, while complying with all ethics and GDPR requirements. Consent will be asked during data collection
- In regard to the project deliverables, all of them will be secured stored in Teamwork. Public deliverables will also be shared in Zenodo and Open Research Europe but also published in project website.
- All data will be stored during the project lifetime, (and if there is a need for up to 5 years after the end of the project for final closing activities) after which the data will be permanently removed. If a partner needs any kind of data over the Project duration, then those can be requested from the coordinator.

The above information will be continuedly evaluated during the project lifecycle, based on the partners input in the DMP Registry file, and if needed can be enhanced or changed.

5 Conclusions

This deliverable has described the 5G-ROUTES Data Management Plan to be used in the project. It includes the rules and guidelines under the Data Management, comply with ethics requirements along with a first overview of the data that are created, processed, or utilized and exploited in the project.

Structured approaches ensure that data management will be following the FAIR data principles as defined by the EC. This document also includes all policies that 5G-ROUTES will follow to comply with the protection of personal data as far as the GDPR (regulation) is concerned.

At the time of preparing this deliverable the project has been running for 14 months and the information about the data collection per WP and per partner have been documented in [Section 4.3](#), where the current status of the DMP Registry “live” document is presented.

An updated / final version of the deliverable will be ready in M33 (May 2023). Undoubtedly, Data Management is a continued work where all data and information collected during the project activities will be analyzed, refined and organized into an aggregated dataset which will be stored in a secured data storage accessible to all project partners. To keep track of the collected data, each WP Leader is responsible for defining and describing all collected datasets specific to their individual work package by completing the DMP Registry file. Updating the DMP Registry file every 3 months (or earlier if required) is the responsibility of the WP leaders after collaboration with the partners who participated in the WP, during the entire lifecycle of the projects. Data management and the DMP Registry updates will be continuously monitored by EBOS, as part of the work in WP5.

As part of the DMP the following templates shall be used when conducting trials involving participants from outside the consortium. Those templates were initially established and included in D7.7 and are part of the Ethics Protocol.

- Informed consent form example template
- Anonymous Informed Consent Template
- Non-Anonymous Informed Consent Template

In addition to the above templates, the “Non-Disclosure Agreement for External Advisory Board Members” template shall also be utilized as part of the DMP. This template exists in D8.1 H – Requirement No.1 (Dissemination level: CO). The utilization of the above-mentioned templates supports the synchronization between the DMP and Ethics and make sure that data collection is based on ethics requirements.

6 References

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- [3] Open Research Europe <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>
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- [5] General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), 27 April 2016, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>
- [6] Open Access guidelines for H2020 projects, https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/open-access_en.htm
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- [19] MARCXML (MARC 21 XML Schema), <https://www.loc.gov/standards/marcxml/>
- [20] BibTeX, <http://www.bibtex.org/>
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- [22] DataCite Metadata Schema, <https://schema.datacite.org/>
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Annex 1: DPO Appointment Template

TO: 5G-ROUTES Project Consortium

SUBJECT: Declaration of Compliance with GDPR for the project 5G-ROUTES and DPO Appointment

With this letter, **PARTNER NAME** is declaring their compliance with the GDPR as in force since 01 September 2020 and relating to collection and/or processing of personal data of EU citizens. **PARTNER NAME** is aligned with the GDPR in an approach to ensure that effective measures are in place to protect the personal data of EU members, customers, employees and other stakeholders and ensure their lawful, fair and transparent processing.

As relates to the personal data involved in the 5G-ROUTES [H2020, GA No: 951867] project, PARTNER NAME confirms that:

- An internal policy is in place relating to personal data protection, developed by **PARTNER NAME's** senior management and communicated to all employees through a comprehensive awareness training programme.
- This internal policy is being used as a lawful basis under the GDPR for any data processed.
- All internal staff understand their roles in the processing and protection of personal data, including confidentiality requirements.
- All personal data under processing have been identified, including special categories whenever involved.
- For the cases where processing is based on required consent, **PARTNER NAME** has provisioned the suitable steps to ensure clear, free consent given/recorded in a clear language explaining all the terms and conditions for the personal data processing (including purpose, right to be forgotten, duration, access by third parties, rectification, EC FAIR treatment etc.).
- Planning for data protection is fully foreseen in new or changed services and systems, including keeping use of personal data to the intended purpose as well as protecting it.

PARTNER NAME has the following dedicated DPO, as senior member appointed and with a role fully aligned with Art.39 of GDPR in informing, advising and monitoring data processing compliance.

- Name: xxxxxxxxx
- ID/Date of Birth: xxxxxxxxx
- E-mail: xxxxxxxxx
- Phone Number: xxxxxxxxx

PARTNER NAME commits to continuously developing and improving their data protection policies and controls, guided by legal requirements and updated regulations and the needs and preferences of our partners, members and customers.

Yours sincerely,

Name: xxxxxxxxx

Title: xxxxxxxxx

Date: xxxxxxxxx

SIGNATURE

.....

Annex 2: DPO Per Partner

Organisation	DPO Name	DPO Email
ERICSSON EESTI AS	Ulle Tiitmaa	ulle.tilmaa@ericsson.com
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AIRBUS DEFENCE AND SPACE SAS	Hartwig Oliver Boesl	oliver.boesl@airbus.com
PASAZIERU VILCIENS	Jana Klintaja	jana.klintaja@ldz.lv
ATOS SPAIN SA	Fatima Aparicio Prieto Ricardo Esteban Lopez Crespo	dles-proteccion.datos@atos.net
BRAINSTORM MULTIMEDIA S.L.	Miguel Churruca Soto	mchurruca@brainstorm3d.com
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Annex 3: Data Protection Policy

Introduction

The GDPR is the EU Regulation that governs the privacy and security of personal data and it is applied by all members states. Alongside the GDPR national laws add to the specifications of data privacy and protection at each member state. Ever since its enforcement in 2018, the GDPR has forced organizations to think twice on the reasons they collect and process data restricting collection and processing to the minimum amount necessary. Additionally, the GDPR assigns nine rights to the data subjects which they can exercise at any point, granting them control of processing of their own data. For the purposes of this Policy the GDPR definitions, as set in Article 4, apply. In addition, the following are applied:

- **“Personal data”** means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person that is processed by any Project Partner and Policy Recipient during execution of the Project.
- **“Controller”** means the owner of the data (usually the creator of the data itself), unless otherwise expressly clarified in this Policy or elsewhere in Project deliverables and/or reports.
- **“Processor”** means each Project Partner, unless otherwise expressly clarified in this Policy or elsewhere in Project deliverables and/or reports.
- **“Consent”** of the data subject means any freely given, specific, informed, unambiguous and **in writing** indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her.
- **“Supervisory authority”** means the competent Data Protection Authorities within the Project Partners’ jurisdictions.

Definitions

Article 4 of the GDPR defines the terms used within the Regulation. Relevant definitions to this project are listed below:

- **personal data** as “any information relating to natural persons, that is or can be identified, even indirectly, by reference to any other information including a personal identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person
- **Special categories of data:** Special categories of personal data include data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation as well as the processing of genetic data and biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying an individual. In the event of such processing the Controller and/or Processor respectively comply with specific rules related to the processing of such data of special categories, as collecting specific informed consent from data subject and applying stricter safeguards. When the Controller and/or Processor relies on data subject's consent as a legal ground for processing special categories of data, it will meet all legal consent requirements; otherwise, they are only processed if and to the extent it is based on one of the legal grounds listed in the GDPR for the processing of such data.
- **Data processing** means any operation, or set of operations, carried out with or without the help of electronic or automated means, concerning the collection, recording, organization, keeping, interrogation, elaboration, modification, selection, retrieval, comparison, utilization, interconnection, blocking, communication, dissemination, erasure and destruction of data whether the latter are contained or not in data bank.
- **Data anonymisation:** Whenever possible, including non-detrimental to Project execution purposes, Controller and Project Partners shall undertake efforts to keep personal data processed by them for Project purposes anonymous or pseudonymous. According to the GDPR, “*anonymous information*” is

information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person, or personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable. In this context, the GDPR does not apply to the processing of such anonymous information, including for statistical or research purposes. Similarly, “*pseudonymisation*” means the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person.

- **Controller:** By determining the purposes and means of the processing of personal data, unless otherwise expressly specified in this Policy, the Controller is considered by law as the “Controller” and it is the primary target of the provisions of the law.
- **Joint controller:** In the event that at any time during Project execution the Controller processes personal data in conjunction with a third party, by jointly determining the purposes and means of the processing, they both act as joint controller. Both joint controllers determine the mutual responsibilities with a specific arrangement.
- **Processor:** Unless otherwise specified expressly in this Policy, all Project Partners act as Processors during Project execution. A processor processes personal data on behalf of the Controller – that is, the Controller delegates all or part of the processing activities to them. In such event the Project contract assumes the role of the relevant required written agreement as per GDPR requirements. The processor warrants that it shall provide sufficient guarantees to ensure compliance with the GDPR, has implemented appropriate controls to meet data protection requirements defined by the agreement, instructions and/or legal requirements and ensures the protection of the rights of data subjects.
- **Data Protection Officer (DPO):** Whenever required, following applicable GDPR and Member State respective legal requirements, the Controller and each Processor, may designate a data protection officer (“DPO”) for assistance in monitoring internal compliance with GDPR.

Lawfulness of Processing

The GDPR restricts processing of personal data if it cannot be justified by one of the legal bases listed in Article 6 on the lawfulness of processing. Therefore, processing shall be lawful only if and to the extent that at least one of the following applies:

- a) The data subject has given consent to the processing of his or her personal data for one or more specific purposes.
- b) Processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering a contract.
- c) Processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject.
- d) Processing is necessary to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person.
- e) Processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller.
- f) Processing is necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests³ pursued by the controller or by a third party, except where such interests are overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject which require protection of personal data, where the data subject is a child.

Notice and Consent

³ If “legitimate interest” is used as a basis, the interests that have preceded to the decision, need to be documented as well as any possible mitigating measures which will be taken to be able to proceed with personal data processing based on the defined interests.

Notice: Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, provides the information required by law to the data subject in a concise, transparent, intelligible, and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language, for any information addressed specifically to a child. The data protection notice informs data subjects about the processing of personal data relating to them, even when the personal data are not collected from them as well as of their rights, to let them verify the accuracy of the data and the lawfulness of the processing.

Free and informed consent: Personal data are processed if and to the extent that the data subject has given valid consent to the processing for one or more specific purposes, or another legal basis for processing exists. Systems or applications can document the explicit consent of the data subject so that it can be evidenced at any time.

The data subject has the right to withdraw their consent at any time without affecting the lawfulness of data processing based on consent before its withdrawal.

Rights of Data Subjects

The GDPR requires that each Controller and/or Processor as appropriate, must facilitate the exercise of the data subject's rights, act on the request within a specific time frame and must communicate the information requested in an intelligible and easy to access form.

Right of access: Any individual must be able to exercise the right of access to data relating to him which are being processed.

Right to rectification: Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for data subjects to request rectification of their personal data. The procedure specifies in which cases rectification is legitimate. If a data subject's request for rectification is legitimate, this is executed across all relevant data storage facilities, including those managed by third parties.

Right to erasure: Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for data subjects to request erasure of their personal data. The procedure specifies in which cases erasure is legitimate. If a data subject's request for erasure is legitimate, this is executed across all relevant data storage facilities, including those managed by third parties.

Right to restriction of processing: Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for data subjects to request restriction of processing of their personal data. The procedure specifies in which cases restriction is legitimate. If a data subject's request for restriction of processing is legitimate, this is executed across all relevant data storage facilities, including those managed by third parties.

Right to data portability: Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, determines which processes are subject to the right of data portability as well as when the requirements for such right are met. Data subject can request the organization to receive a machine-readable copy of the personal data the organization holds about them and where possible, enable the transfer of this data to another data controller.

Portability right can be exercised when:

- a) Processing operations are based on data subject's consent or on contract.
- b) Personal data concerns the data subject and are the same that the latter has provided to the organization.
- c) The right does not adversely affect rights and freedoms of others.
- d) The processing is carried out by automated means.

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, implements appropriate measures and procedures to provide data subject, who is entitled to, with a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable copy of the personal data it holds about him and where possible, to enable the transfer of this data to another data controller indicated by data subject.

Right to object: Where personal data are processed for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, the data subjects have the right to object on grounds relating to their situation (unless the processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out for reasons of public interest). The right to object is explicitly brought to the attention of the data subject at the latest at the time of the first communication with the data subject, presented clearly and separately from any other information. Measures should be in place to assess such objections and to ensure that such processing ceases when the request is legitimate and needs to be respected. Data subjects have right to object, on request and free of charge, to the processing of personal data relating to them for purposes of direct marketing.

Automated decision making: Data subject has the right to object to any automatic decision-making (including profiling). Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, will have determined which processes entail automated decision-making (including profiling) and will have established measures to allow data subjects to object to such automated decision making and profiling. Suitable measures are in place to safeguard the data subject's rights and freedoms and legitimate interest, at least the right to obtain human intervention on the part of the Company/controller, to express his or her point of view and to contest the decision.

Timely response to exercise of rights: Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, must confirm to data subjects without delay whether data relating to them are processed and communicate the data to them in an intelligible form. Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should implement internal procedures in order to be able to provide a timely response to the requests of data subject for the exercise of his rights. Measures have to be implemented in a way that effectively allows an individual to exercise his or her right to personal data, and that enables Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, to respond to such request appropriately within the required timeframes.

Notification to recipients: In case of a legitimate exercise of rights to rectification, erasure, or restriction of processing recipients of the personal data should be informed of the rectification, erasure of that data or of the restriction of processing. Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for communicating any rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing to the recipients to whom the personal data has been disclosed and for disclosing these recipients to the data subject, if so requested. Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, about their processing activities must set up a relevant record, maintained in writing (including in electronic form) and made available easily and swiftly to the supervisory authority on request, as per applicable legal requirements within their respective Member States. The record of processing activities shall contain all the information required by GDPR. Consequently, the Controller shall have an up-to-date overview of all personal data processing activities and shall maintain records within the Project, that meet the legal requirements posed by the GDPR. By so doing, the Controller will be able to demonstrate compliance to any Supervisory Authority or other state or EU authority concerned. For the avoidance of doubt, each Project Partner carries the same responsibility above within its own respective organisation.

Data protection assessment

Article 35 of the GDPR refers to the need for a Data Privacy Impact Assessment (DPIA). This refers to the obligation of the controller to conduct an impact assessment and to document it before starting the intended data processing. The DPIA assesses the risks of data processing alongside the impact to the data subject and it is required in case of:

- a) Systematic and extensive evaluation of personal aspects relating to natural persons which is based on automated processing, including profiling, and on which decisions are based that produce legal effects concerning the natural person or similarly significantly affect the natural person.
- b) Processing on a large scale of special categories of data referred to in Article 9(1), or of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences referred to in Article 10; or
- c) Systematic monitoring of a publicly accessible area on a large scale.

Technical and organizational measures

The Controller and each Project Partner, as appropriate, adopts appropriate technical and organisational measures about Project execution (the “**Measures**”), and reviews and updates them where necessary, to ensure and to be able to demonstrate that processing is complying with GDPR. Each Project Partner shall notify relevant Measures to the Controller in writing. In the event of any queries or further requests by the Controller, each Project Partner undertakes to address them duly and in writing. If any Project Partner has notified the Measures to its competent Supervisory Authority, it shall inform the Controller thereof, and shall provide respective copies thereof.

Data breach

According to the GDPR, all organizations processing personal data must have appropriate and adequate measures to prevent any attempts of personal data breaches. In the event of a data breach, mechanisms must be in place to mitigate the risks and minimize the impact on the data subject. Additionally, in the event of a data breach the responsible Controller or Processor must notify their local Supervisory Authority immediately and not later than 72 hours after they become aware of the breach. If the breach carries significant risk of serious adverse effects on the data subject(s) or serious adverse consequences for the protection of personal data, the data subject must also be informed without undue delay. A specific register where the breaches must be recorded together with other information specified by the law, must be maintained by the Controller, and shown to the Supervisory Authority upon request. This register is an important element of the data protection documentation system. Project Partners need to notify immediately and in writing the Controller of any personal data breach within their respective organisations that affects execution of the Project in any way, and to cooperate with the Controller while applying relevant GDPR legal requirements.

Data to Third Countries

No international transfers of personal data are expected to take place during the Project lifecycle. In case that a Project Partner wishes to carry out such personal data processing, it shall notify the Project Coordinator in writing and in advance. Moreover, no server utilized by the Project, or file repository is located outside the EU.

Project Website and Cloud File Repository

Project website and document server includes privacy and cookies policies and are available in the following URLs:

- Project website Privacy Policy: <https://www.5g-routes.eu/privacy-policy/>
- Project website Cookies Policy: <https://www.5g-routes.eu/cookies-policy/>

Project cloud file repository of the Project (Teamwork) also provides privacy policies and GDPR compliance in the following URLs:

- Teamwork Privacy Policy: <https://www.teamwork.com/legal/privacy-policy/>
- Teamwork GDPR Compliance : <https://www.teamwork.com/legal/gdpr/>